

Studies of *Bis-N-Phenylhydroxamic Acid* as Metal Complexing Ligands, Part V: Studies of the Coloured Ternary Complexes of Ti(IV) with Pimelyl-bis-*N-phenylhydroxamic Acid*

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Manuscript received 30 August 1972; revised 12 February 1973; accepted 2 May 1973

Titanium (IV) is extractable with chloroform from 7.5 N HCl solution by simultaneous use of pimelyl-bis-*N-phenylhydroxamic acid* (R_pH_2) and NaN_3 , yielding a deep yellow extract. The composition of the yellow coloured Ti(IV) complex formed in presence of excess of NaN_3 , has been found to be 1 : 2 [Ti(IV) : R_pH_2] complex by Job's method of continuous variation.

STUDIES of the chelating properties¹ as well as an analytical application of pimelyl-bis-*N-phenylhydroxamic acid*² (R_pH_2) have been reported earlier. Now it has been found that Ti(IV) can be extracted into chloroform with this reagent R_pH_2 from 7.5 N HCl medium but the extinction is very low. However, the simultaneous use of R_pH_2 and NaN_3 makes the colour of Ti(IV) complex intense and it is much more rapidly extractable. The ratio of Ti(IV) : ligand in this complex has been determined in the presence of excess of NaN_3 by a physico-chemical method due to Job³.

Experimental

Reagent : The ligand R_pH_2 was prepared following the method described earlier¹ and other reagents were either A.R. quality or properly purified. Freshly prepared ligand solution in chloroform and 25% aqueous solution of NaN_3 were used. A 0.0373 M stock solution of Ti(IV) in 2N HCl was prepared. It was used for the preparation of Ti(IV) solution of required strengths in 6N HCl.

Apparatus : Optical densities were measured with a spectrophotometer (UVISPEK) using 1 cm quartz cell.

Procedure : Equimolecular solutions ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of Ti(IV) in 6N HCl and of the ligand R_pH_2 in chloroform were prepared for the study of the spectral curves of mixtures containing Ti(IV), R_pH_2 and NaN_3 solution.

Different volumes of ligand solutions were mixed with 2 ml portions of Ti(IV) solution in a separatory funnel. Requisite quantities of conc. HCl, NaN_3

and water were added so that the aqueous layer had a total volume of 20 ml, it was 7.5N with respect to HCl and contained 0.03 g of NaN_3 per ml. Measured volumes of $CHCl_3$ were then added to keep the volume of the organic layer 10 ml in each case before extractions. The mixture was then shaken vigorously, layers allowed to separate, organic layer transferred to a conical flask. The aqueous layer was

Fig. 1. $NaN_3 = 0.03$ g/ml of aq. layer. Initial conc. of Ti(IV) and $R_pH_2 = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, HCl = 7.5N. Vols. of Ti(IV) soln. = 2.0 ml. Final vol. of $CHCl_3 = 25$ ml.

Curve	Ti(IV) ml : R_pH_2 ml.
I	2.0 : 2.0
II	2.0 : 4.0
III	2.0 : 6.0
IV	2.0 : 8.0
V	2.0 : 10.0

washed with 5 ml portions of CHCl_3 , washings were collected in the same conical flask. The extract was dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The volume was finally made up to 25 ml. Optical densities against water were measured in the range 360–500 nm.

Spectral absorption curves are shown in Fig. 1. From the curves λ values of 450 and 480 nm were selected for further studies.

Determination of metal : ligand ratio in the complex

Two sets of equimolecular solutions (one set being $8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and another set being $3.2 \times 10^{-3} M$) of metal and ligand were mixed in different ratios in a separatory funnel, keeping the total volume 10 ml. Requisite volumes of NaN_3 solution, conc. HCl and water were added so that the aqueous layer had a volume of 20 ml, it was 7.5N with respect to HCl and contained 0.03 g of NaN_3 per ml as before. Measured volumes of CHCl_3 were then added to keep the volume of the organic layer 10 ml in each case before extraction. It was then extracted as usual and final volume of CHCl_3 extract was made 25 ml.

Optical densities at the wavelengths of 450 and 480 nm of the extracts were measured against water. The volumes after correction for ligands were plotted as a function of the composition of the mixture (Fig. 2 with respect to $8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution). Similar curves were also obtained with $3.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution. Metal : Ligand ratio in the coloured complex has been found to be 1 : 2.

But from the nature of the curves obtained the existence of a 1 : 1 complex could not be ruled out. The curves are deviated from the ideal ones with inflexions at the composition just beyond 1 : 1.

From Fig. 1, it is apparent that on increasing ligand concentration, O.D. values slowly rise to a maximum one and then begin to decrease. This interesting

Fig. 2. $\text{NaN}_3 = 0.03$ g/ml of aq. layer

Initial conc. of Ti(IV) and $R_pH_2 = 8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
Final vol. of $\text{CHCl}_3 = 25$ ml.

observations is probably associated to structural changes as well as the composition of species.

References

1. N. N. GHOSH and D. K. SARKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 562.
2. N. N. GHOSH and D. K. SARKAR, *Science and Culture*, 1970, **36**, 522.
3. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim*, 1928, **9**, 113.